

Stata Tutorial - Spatial Regression Discontinuity Design

Replicating the Moscona, Nunn and Robinson (2020) study
”Segmentary lineage organization and conflict in sub-Saharan
Africa”

Contents

1	Spatial Regression Discontinuity Design Theory	2
2	Introduction	3
2.1	Hypothesis: Ethnic Groups organized around Segmentary Lineages are more prone to conflict	3
2.2	Data: Conflict and Ethnic Groups in sub-Saharan Africa	4
3	Replication	5
3.1	Preparation of the data : Creations of locals	5
3.2	First tests: OLS estimates	5
3.2.1	Perform the regressions	6
3.2.2	Creation of the table	8
3.3	Second tests : Spatial RDD	11
3.3.1	Creation of Polynomials	11
3.3.2	Graphs representation	12
3.3.3	Sharp RD	14
3.3.4	Fuzzy RDD	15
3.4	Third tests - Placebo Tests	18
A	Esttab	19
A.1	Esttab Sharp RD	19
A.2	Esttab Fuzzy RDD	19

link to the replication package :

1 Spatial Regression Discontinuity Design Theory

In **spatial Regression Discontinuity Design** (RDD), treatment and control groups are defined at a spatial boundary. Two conditions are needed to apply a regression discontinuity design. First a clearly defined multidimensional cutoff point (longitude and latitude of the boundary), and a continuous eligibility index.

Moreover, the validity of the Spatial RDD design relies crucially on the assumption that those individuals around the **geographical cutoff**, have the same distribution of unobservables as those individuals immediately above the cut-off. In a geographic-based RD design, we compare units in a treated area to units in a control area, thus near the cutoff, the treatment and comparison units are most similar. In other words, spatial heterogeneity is assumed to be relatively constant around the geographical boundary.

To achieve this comparison around the cutoff point, two-dimensional space (latitude and longitude) are reduced to a one-dimensional distance, using Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques. This reduction results in an assignment variable: the distance to the border. Subsequently, standard RDD methods are applied. Thus, units directly to the left and right of the cutoff point should be so similar that the identification of the treatment effect becomes possible without a random process.

The choice of bandwidth is a critical decision that directly influences the estimated treatment effect, as it determines the span of observations considered as being close to the geographical cutoff. A narrow bandwidth focuses on a small range around the cutoff, providing high precision but potentially leading to higher variance. On the other hand, a wide bandwidth includes a larger range, smoothing the treatment effect estimates but potentially introducing bias.

Moreover, there are two different variants of the RDD, **sharp and fuzzy**, that depend on the compliance to ethnic group of individuals close to the ethnicity boundaries. In **sharp designs**, the probability of treatment changes from 0 to 1 at the cutoff. There are no cross-overs and no no-shows. In **fuzzy designs**, the probability of treatment is discontinuous at the cutoff, but not to the degree of a definitive 0 to 1 jump. The fuzziness may result from imperfect compliance

Finally, **Placebo tests** are really important when using Spatial RDD as identification strategy, to convince that the discontinuity exploited to inform causal impacts of a treatment was very much likely caused by the assignment to the treatment group. Standard balance checks on covariates or outcomes which should not be affected by the treatment are an important validation of the design.

2 Introduction

2.1 Hypothesis: Ethnic Groups organized around Segmentary Lineages are more prone to conflict

In their article, Moscona, Nunn, and Robinson explore the relationship between conflict and the kinship structure of societies in sub-Saharan Africa, specifically focusing on whether an ethnic group is organized into segmentary lineages. The hypothesis considers that due to their structure, these ethnic groups are more susceptible to conflict as mobilizing combatants during a conflict becomes easier and faster. While in Western cultures, dominant social relations are based on the nuclear family, in the rest of the world, people live among a much more complex and connected social structure within a network. This structure is named as segmentary lineage organization.

According to the authors, an ethnic group is coded as a segmentary lineage society if there are direct evidences of the following three characteristics :

- There is a unilineal descent, from whom people trace their ancestry either through the male line, called patrilineal, or through the female line, called matrilineal; but never both. This ancestry is often common and mythical, seen as a pillar on which the foundations of societies and tribes rest.
- The segments of the lineage must take a "corporate form", which are independent from each other and are important to the formation of political, administrative, and judicial functions.
- There is evidence that there is a geographic organization of residence that is based on the lineage and genealogical relationship system.

To illustrate the previous explanation before going forward, let's see the following explanation of the authors :

"An important aspect of segmentary lineage societies is that lineages and segments, and one's responsibility to them, are of the utmost importance. In the figure, if individual i were to have a dispute with individual ix within a segmentary lineage system, this would mean that all individuals belonging to Major Segment A would be allied with and come to the defense of individual i . Similarly, all individuals in Major Segment B would be allied with and come to the defense of individual ix . Thus, a dispute between two individuals escalates into a dispute between two large communities. Outside of segmentary lineage systems, where these allegiances are absent, the dispute might comprise, at most, a small number of friends or immediate family members of the two individuals involved in the dispute"

Figure 1: A representation of a hypothetical segmentary lineage society. (Moskana and al., 2020)

An Application of Spatial Regression Discontinuity Design in Sub-Saharan Africa:

In the context of this study, geographic ethnic boundaries are used as cutoffs. The treatment refers to the presence of segmentary lineage organization. The sample comprises 68 grid cells, each measuring 10 km by 10 km, situated in proximity to ethnic boundaries. The methodology involves a comparison between geographically close locations, where one is inhabited by a segmentary lineage society and the other by a society without segmentary lineages. The primary objective is to evaluate the causal effect of segmentary lineage organization on the incidence of conflict from 1997 to 2014, utilizing the estimated difference in conflict at the ethnic boundary. This approach offers the advantage of accounting for unobservable factors that exhibit smooth variations across space. It is important to consider that within segmentary lineage territory, when one is close to the border, much less than 100% of the population belongs to a segmentary lineage group.

2.2 Data: Conflict and Ethnic Groups in sub-Saharan Africa

The data utilized in this study are sourced from the 'Ethnographic Survey of Africa' by Daryll Forbes and the 'Ethnographic Atlas.' The researchers successfully coded 145 ethnic groups, with 74 identified as segmentary lineage societies, constituting 38% of Sub-Saharan Africa, and 71 not organized in this manner. Additionally, conflict data were obtained from the Armed Conflict Location and Event Data Project (ACLED), a geo-coded dataset cataloging information about each conflict event in Africa from January 1, 1997, to December 31, 2014.

3 Replication

3.1 Preparation of the data : Creations of locals

In Stata, the 'local' command is used to define local macros. Local macros serve as temporary storage spaces where you can store text strings or values that you want to reuse later in your Stata program. These macro will be used to reference these variables throughout the Stata code, making it easier to manage and modify them.

```
Defining local of our variables of interest
local all_conflict = "ln_conflict_fatal log_fatalities ln_cfatm"

Defining control variables for analysis
local fe = "i.ccode"
local geo = "ln_shape_area ln_dist_kilometers meanalt SI abs_lat lon
            split10pc sc_mean"
local hist = "v33 v30 patrilineal"
```

As you can see, 4 locals are created, one for the variables of interest, and three for the control variables :

- `all_conflict` macro, containing a space-separated list of variables of interest.
- `fe` macro contains the variable `i.ccode`.
- `geo` macro contains a list of geographical variables.
- `hist` macro stores variables related to history.

Local variables are often employed in loops and macros to create flexible and reusable scripts. They enable the dynamic parameterization of certain parts of the code.

3.2 First tests: OLS estimates

The first equation they test is a simple OLS to study the relationship between segmentary lineage organization and conflict today using the equation 2.

$$y_i = \alpha_{c(i)} + \beta I_i^{SL} + \mathbf{X}_i' \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where i denotes ethnic groups, c denotes countries, y_i denotes one of our 12 measures of conflict experienced by ethnic group i , I_i^{SL} is an indicator variable that equals 1 if ethnic group i is traditionally organized into segmentary lineages and 0 if it is not, $\alpha_{c(i)}$ denotes country fixed effects, and \mathbf{X}_i' is a vector of ethnicity-level historical and geographic covariates. The coefficient of interest is beta. A positive coefficient indicates that segmentary lineage societies experience more conflict.

3.2.1 Perform the regressions

The initial step involves replicating the first row of table 2 from the paper. Let's conduct three separate regressions for the three distinct dependent variables.

Table 1: replication of the line 1 of table 2

Dependent Variable:	ln (1+Deadly Conflict Incidents)			ln (1+Conflict Deaths)			ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Segmentary Lineage (=1)	1.147*** (0.294)	1.146*** (0.217)	1.102*** (0.245)	1.627*** (0.467)	1.685*** (0.375)	1.439*** (0.420)	0.905*** (0.240)	0.890*** (0.176)	0.869*** (0.195)
Jurisdictional Hierarchy			-0.064 (0.122)			-0.303 (0.186)			-0.013 (0.096)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Geographic controls	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Historical controls	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Mean of Dep. Var.	2.56	2.56	2.56	4.01	4.01	4.01	2.16	2.16	2.16
Observations	145	145	141	145	145	141	145	145	141
R-squared	0.530	0.705	0.717	0.555	0.694	0.716	0.525	0.713	0.726

Notes: Robust standard errors in parenthesis. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

To optimize our code, we utilize a loop for performing the multiple regressions and storing the results, while tracking the use of additional controls.

```
capture estimates drop est*
```

First, drop all existing estimation results starting with "est" : EXPLAIN WHY ?

```
foreach var in `all_conflict' {
  eststo : reg `var' SL `fe',r
  sum `var'
  estadd scalar mean=r(mean)
  estadd local coufe "Yes"
  estadd local geoco "No"
  estadd local hisco "No"

  eststo : reg `var' SL `fe' `geo',r
  sum `var'
  estadd scalar mean=r(mean)
  estadd local coufe "Yes"
  estadd local geoco "Yes"
  estadd local hisco "No"

  eststo : reg `var' SL `fe' `geo' `hist',r
  sum `var'
  estadd scalar mean=r(mean)
  estadd local coufe "Yes"
  estadd local geoco "Yes"
  estadd local hisco "Yes"
}
```

Making the loop allows to iterate over each variable (`var`) within the `'all_conflict'` local. For each variable, the loop executes three consecutive linear regressions:

- The first regression comprises fixed effects specified by `'SL'` and the dependent variable `'var'`.
- The second regression comprise countries fixed effects specified by `'geo'`.
- The third regression incorporates historical effects specified by `'hist'`.

What is performed within the loop ?

- we make and store the regression, `'eststo'` will store the regression under the name `'est1'` made by calling the first variable of the local `'all_conflict'` by `'var'`, `'SL'` is the variable of interest (=1 if lineage in the ethnic) and `'fe'` is a local containing qualitative variables (used as country fixed effect). The `'r'` after the comma tells us that all standard errors are robust.
 - The command `'sum var'` is equivalent to `'summarize,'` providing descriptive statistics for the dependent variable.
 - `'estadd scalar mean=r(mean)'` is here to save under the name `'mean'` the mean of the dependent variable.
 - Local variables (`'estadd local'`) are also used to indicate the presence or absence of fixed effects (`'coufe'`), geographical effects (`'geoco'`), and historical effects (`'hisco'`) in each regression.
 - * `'coufe'` is an arbitrary name
 - * you have to manually precise if you use or not any fixed effect or control by changing `'Yes'` by `'No'` or the reverse
 - `estadd local geoco "No"` & `estadd local hisco "No"` are the same as before, just they refer to other local.
- And we do that for as many regressions we need to perform, here 2 other.

The results of each regression are captured and stored using the `eststo` command.

In summary, this script performs a series of linear regressions for different variables, progressively adding fixed, geographical, and historical effects. The results of each regression are stored, and additional information is added for each model. The `'foreach'` loop facilitates the automation of this process for all variables specified in `'all_conflict'`. And, of course, the loop will end when all variables are used in the regressions.

Thus, our regression allows us to conclude on a positive and significant relationship between the presence of segmentary lineage organization and conflict.

3.2.2 Creation of the table

Let's now dive into a complicated stuff, making 'great' tables from Stata to Latex. It is important to note that our replication of the table is not necessary the same, they only gave us excel table, and sometimes, researchers build their table by hand to be published. Still, when you are making you own work, it is essential to enhance our proficiency in converting statistical output from Stata into well-organized tables using LaTeX. It's always nice, even for some preliminary results to look at pretty tables.

We provide you with an example of what you can do, be aware that you still need to adjust manually this example if you want to use it for an other table. To initiate this process, ensure that you have the esttab package installed in your Stata environment.

```
scc install esttab

esttab est* using "YourPath/table1.tex", cells(b(fmt(3) star) se(par fmt
(3))) stats(oufe geoco hisco mean N r2 , fmt(%9.0gc %9.0gc %9.0gc
%9.2f %-9.0gc %9.3f) label("Country FE" "Geographic controls" "
Historical controls" "Mean of Dep. Var." "Observations" "R-squared"))
replace style(tex) label collabels(none) mlabels(none) keep(SL v33)
prehead( `"\begin{table}[htbp]\centering" ' `"\def\sym#1{\ifmode^{#1}\
else\(^{#1}\)\fi}" ' `"\caption{replication of the line 1 of table 2}" '
`"\resizebox{\columnwidth}{!}{%" ' `"\begin{tabular}{1*{9}{c}}" ' `"\
toprule" ' `"Dependent Variable: &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Deadly
Conflict Incidents)} &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Conflict Deaths)} &
\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)} \\" ' `"\
cmidrule(lr){2-4} \cmidrule(lr){5-7} \cmidrule(lr){8-10} " ' ) postfoot
(`"\bottomrule" ' `"\multicolumn{10}{l}{\footnotesize Notes: Robust
standard errors in parenthesis. \sym{*} \(\p<0.10\), \sym{**} \(\p<0.05\)\
, \sym{***} \(\p<0.01\)}\\" ' `"\end{tabular}}" ' `"\end{table}" ' )
```

What this ugly code makes ?

- 'est*' will call all estimates store, here from est1 to est9. Once you call them put 'using "Your-Path/table1.tex",' you may want to replace YourPath by a global created before, and will make store your table in a specific file.
- 'cells(b(fmt(3) star) se(par fmt(3)))'
 - 'b(fmt(3) star)' means that you want to store the data 'b' meaning the coefficient with 3 digits after the comma, and to put stars on those coefficient depending on their significancy.
 - se(par fmt(3)) tells that you also want to store the standard deviation, with 3 digits after the comma.
- 'stats(oufe geoco hisco mean N r2 , fmt(%9.0gc %9.0gc %9.0gc %9.2f %-9.0f %9.3f) label("Country FE" "Geographic controls" "Historical controls" "Mean of Dep. Var." "Observations" "R-squared"))'

- `stats(coufe geoco hisco mean N r2 , fmt(%9.0gc %9.0gc %9.0gc %9.2f %-9.0gc %9.3f)` tells that you want to put in the table all 'esttad' created before, the number of observations and the R squared. For the `fmt`, this tell us in what format they will be stored. '9.0gc' is for a text. '9.2f' is for numbers, we specified that we want 2 digits after the comma¹.
- `'label("Country FE" "Geographic controls" "Historical controls" "Mean of Dep. Var." "Observations" "R-squared")'` is to change the name by something more comprehensive for our stats, it has to in the same order as you call them before.
- 'replace' tells stata to replace if a file with the same name already exists
- 'style(tex)' tells that it's going to be a tex file (to be used by latex)
- 'label' specify that you want to use the label of each variables in the table and not their name.
- 'collabels(none)' make disappear 'b/se', which are the stats that you have in your table.
- 'mlabels(none)' make disappear the name of the dependant variable for each column. (Which would have made the table super long)
- 'keep(SL v33)' indicate that we only want to keep coefficient associated with those variable.

With what is describe above you have already make a good filter on your table. But, if you want to modify it more, you need to use you latex knowledge. This start with the 'prehead'. In the code below, you can see that all arguments are between : "' argument "'. Make sure to don't forget that. The first part is always needed to make a table on stata.

```
prehead( `"\begin{table}[htbp]\centering" ' `"\def\sym#1{\ifmmode ^{#1}\else
\(^{#1}\)\fi}" ' `"\caption{replication of the line 1 of table 2}" '
`\resizebox{\columnwidth}{!}{%" ' `"\begin{tabular}{1*{9}{c}}" ' `"\
toprule" ' `"\Dependent Variable: &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Deadly
Conflict Incidents)} &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Conflict Deaths)} &
\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)} \\" ' `"\
cmidrule(lr){2-4} \cmidrule(lr){5-7} \cmidrule(lr){8-10} " ' ) postfoot
(`"\bottomrule" ' `"\multicolumn{10}{1}{\footnotesize Notes: Robust
standard errors in parenthesis. \sym{*} \ (p<0.10\), \sym{**} \ (p<0.05\),
\sym{***} \ (p<0.01\)}\\" ' `"\end{tabular}}" ' `"\end{table}" ' )
```

The number '9' below has to be changed manually with respect with the number of columns you have in your table.

```
`"\begin{tabular}{1*{9}{c}}" '
```

¹you can check 'help fmt' on stata to see other formats

This has be add to match the paper table. Basically, I put on the right 'Dependent Variable:', After, for groups of 3² columns that share the same dependant variable, I precise the name of it. The functions after are creating lines for each groups of 3 variables³. This part is not mandatory at all, but still good to know.

```

`"Dependent Variable: &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Deadly Conflict
Incidents)} &\multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Conflict Deaths)} &\
multicolumn{3}{c}{ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)} \\ " ' ` " \
cmidrule(lr){2-4} \cmidrule(lr){5-7} \cmidrule(lr){8-10} " '

```

You precise until which column your foot note can goes⁴.

```

`"\multicolumn{10}{1}{\footnotesize Notes: Robust standard errors in
parenthesis. \sym{*} \ (p<0.10\), \sym{**} \ (p<0.05\), \sym{***} \ (
p<0.01\)} \\ " ' ` "\end{tabular}}" '

```

²You can change the number to 5 if the same dependant variable is used 5 time in 'multicolumn3'

³we start at 2 because here, the column of variable names is counted as column 1

⁴Here 10, same explanation as above

3.3 Second tests : Spatial RDD

Despite the robustness of our OLS estimates and the consistency of findings across various observable characteristics, a concern pertains to the potential impact of unobservables that may introduce bias into their estimates.

”For example, if ethnic groups have a persistent unobservable propensity to engage in conflict and if this affected whether ethnic groups adopted a segmentary lineage organization in the past, then this unobservable trait could bias our estimates of interest. In this case, we would observe a relationship between segmentary lineage systems and conflict even if no causal relationship exists. Such unobservable traits could originate from a range of different sources, including the physical environment or historical experiences”

Thus, in response to the challenge posed by potential effect of unobservable factors, the strategy undertaken is to compare locations that are geographically close, but where one location is inhabited by a segmentary lineage society and the other does not. As the authors are looking at the causal impact, the identification strategy to go for it is a spatial Regression Discontinuity Design (RDD) which permit to restricts the sample to 10-km by 10-km grid cell that are sufficiently close to the ethnic boundaries and estimates.

$$y_{ip} = \omega_p + \gamma I_{i(p)}^{SL} + f(location_{ip}) + \mathbf{Z}'_i \mathbf{\Gamma} + \varepsilon_{ip} \quad (2)$$

They have before computed on a different software the distance of the minimum distance between the ethnic group centroid and a ethnic border.

3.3.1 Creation of Polynomials

There are created from the near_dist variable which report the distance from the border of an other ethnicities. When we use a RDD, there is one function before the cutoff and one after the cutoff. If we for example want to show a graph, we need to distinguish from the two. So, positive values imply kilometers into the territory of the segmentary lineage society and negative values are kilometers into the nonsegmentary lineage society. In this paper, their main polynomial function is a local polynomial, they multiply the distance by 1000. The code below show how they created their 2 variables.

- First of all, the variable ,near_dist_km is created, it takes the value of the distance, negative for nonsegmentary lineage society, the reverse when the society is organize in lineage form.
- with the variable created, lets create the 2 polynomial functions, both are multiplied by 1000 (local polynomial):
 - near_dist_sign takes the value of near_dist_km multiplied by 1000
 - near_dist_sign_seg takes the value of near_dist_km multiplied by 1000 only for segmentary lineage society. (kind of an interacted term)

```

gen near_dist_km = - near_dist if SL ==0
replace near_dist_km = near_dist if SL==1
gen near_dist_sign = near_dist_km * 1000
gen near_dist_sign_seg = near_dist_km * 1000 if SL==1
replace near_dist_sign_seg = 0 if SL==0

```

The spatial RD estimates of the effect of segmentary lineage organization on conflict are qualitatively identical to the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimates. The relationships between segmentary lineage organization and our measures of conflict are all positive and highly significant. The findings are robust to different bandwidths and to different methods of controlling for the two-dimensional running variables.

3.3.2 Graphs representation

One of the biggest advantages of an RDD is the graphical representation of results. Below is the combination of 4 graphs with the four different outcomes unconditionally of the distance from the border. The y-axis reports the natural log of 1 plus the number of deadly conflict incidents for each of the four different types of conflict. The x-axis reports distance (in kilometers) from the borders between segmentary lineage and nonsegmentary lineage societies. The border is at kilometer 0, and positive values indicate kilometers in the territories of segmentary lineage societies.

Figure 2: Binned scatterplots (with 20 bins) of the unconditional relationship between conflict incidence and distance from the border.

```
gen figure_sample = near_dist_sign_km<150 & near_dist_sign_km>-150
```

Because it is not really serious to compare societies living really far from each other, they decided to make a sample for the graph. The code do do that is creating a dummy that is equal to 1 if the condition is completed. The code is below, you don't need to inform the value that the variable will take, stata make it equal to one by default.

```
binscatter ln_sum_deadly near_dist_sign_km if figure_sample==1, rd(0)
  ytitle(ln(1+Deadly Conflict Incidents)) xtitle(Distance to Border (km))
  xlabel(-150 -100 -50 0 50 100 150)
graph save Figure6a.gph,replace
binscatter ln_civf near_dist_sign_km if figure_sample==1, rd(0) ytitle(ln
  (1+Deadly Civil Conflict Incidents)) xtitle(Distance to Border (km))
  xlabel(-150 -100 -50 0 50 100 150)
graph save Figure6b.gph,replace
binscatter ln_noncivf near_dist_sign_km if figure_sample==1, rd(0) ytitle(
  ln(1+Deadly Non-Civil Conflict Incidents)) xtitle(Distance to Border (
  km)) xlabel(-150 -100 -50 0 50 100 150)
graph save Figure6c.gph,replace
binscatter ln_ethf near_dist_sign_km if figure_sample==1, rd(0) ytitle(ln
  (1+Deadly Within-Group Conflict Incidents)) xtitle(Distance to Border (
  km)) xlabel(-150 -100 -50 0 50 100 150)
graph save Figure6d.gph,replace
graph combine Figure6a.gph Figure6b.gph Figure6c.gph Figure6d.gph
```

In this code, we are doing 4 times the same one, but changing the variable of the y axis, and the title of it. If we decompose the code, 'binscatter' is the function to graph scatter plot, 'ln_sum_deadly' is variable for the y axis, 'near_dist_sign_km' is the variable for the x axis.

- 'rd(0)' is used to inform about the discontinuity of the running variable that we are going to use. Here it is the distance from the border.
- 'if figure_sample==1' is to limit the size of the graph.
- ytitle & xtitle : are to give a title to different axis.
- xlabel is to change the value of the axis, if you are not happy with what the software gives you.
- 'graph save XXXXXXXX.gph, replace' is to save the graph. Has to be done for each graph.
- 'graph combine' enable us to merge the four graphs into one. It eases the comparison between the tables and is easier to use on latex.

The positive value on the x axis are for segmentary lineage territory, while the negative distance to border is for nonsegmentary lineage society.

3.3.3 Sharp RD

We are now going to present how to perform the RDD. It's in fact not really different from a simple regression to code.

```
*Defining conflict measures
local all_conflict = "ln_sum_deadly ln_sum_fatal ln_conflictfm"

*Defining cell-level control set
local rd = "elev simean split_grid"

*Panel A - All Conflicts
foreach var in `all_conflict' {
  eststo : reg `var' SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg if
    near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
  estadd local ethfe "Yes"
  estadd local coufe "No"
  estadd local geoco "No"

  eststo : reg `var' SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg i.
    countrycode if near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
  estadd local ethfe "Yes"
  estadd local coufe "Yes"
  estadd local geoco "No"

  eststo : reg `var' SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg i.
    countrycode `rd' if near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
  estadd local ethfe "Yes"
  estadd local coufe "Yes"
  estadd local geoco "Yes"
}
```

The researcher has to pay attention to how the fixed effects are assigned. In this code, we are first creating some locals to make the code clearer. Then we make a loop, that will perform regressions for the 3 types of conflicts.

There is 3 different specifications,

- 1 with only Ethnicity pair fixed effect.
- 1 with Ethnicity pair fixed effect and country fixed effect.
- 1 with both and geographic controls is added.

Except this change, they are all constructed in the same manner, the dependant variable is 'SL' for 'Segmentary Lineage'. Standards errors are clustered at the Ethnicity level with the variable 'NAME'. One specification is related about the bandwidth, they have chosen in the basic results to use 60 kilometers

(meaning 120km max for the 2 extremums) so they restrict the sample of the regressions of observations for which they are at max 60 km of the border with the variable 'near_dst'. The code for the table (esttab) can be found in the appendix A.1.

Table 2: replication of the line 1 of table 2

Dependent Variable:	ln (1+Deadly Conflict Incidents)			ln (1+Conflict Deaths)			ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
SL	0.0420** (0.0158)	0.0373* (0.0153)	0.0378* (0.0152)	0.0862** (0.0283)	0.0791** (0.0283)	0.0805** (0.0278)	0.0323* (0.0128)	0.0283* (0.0126)	0.0287* (0.0124)
Ethnicity Pair FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Geographic Controls	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Observations	10739	10739	10739	10739	10739	10739	10739	10739	10739

Notes: Standard errors, clustered at the ethnicity level, are reported in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

3.3.4 Fuzzy RDD

As you can see, the “sharp” RD coefficients suggest a smaller increase in conflict associated with segmentary lineage organization when compared to the OLS regressions. To explain this difference, one hypothesis proposed is the existence of spillover effects near the borders of segmentary lineage territories, which create imperfect compliance of individuals close to the ethnicity boundaries.

Thus, the author adopts a Fuzzy Regression Discontinuity Design (RDD). This means that instead of a clear-cut, deterministic assignment of individuals to either the treatment or control group based on a strict cutoff point, the assignment (being part of a segmentary lineage) becomes more probabilistic.

Database preparation

```
collapse (sum) match obs (mean) SL near_dist near_dist_sign
near_dist_sign_seg countrycode ln_sum_deadly ln_sum_fatal
ln_conflict_fm (firstnm) NAME, by(pair_fe gridcellid)

gen frac_seg = match/obs
```

The first step involves preparing the data. We use the collapse function to aggregate data at the cell level. Variables specified within the parentheses (e.g., match, obs, SL, etc.) are aggregated using sum or mean as appropriate.

A new variable called "frac_seg" is then created using the gen command. This variable represents the percentage of ethnicities (match) in each cell (obs), helping to assess the relative ethnic composition. This permit to assess the relative ethnic composition in each cell.

```
replace near_dist_sign = near_dist_sign/1000
replace near_dist = near_dist/1000
```

To facilitate subsequent analysis, with the command "replace", we adjust the `near_dist_sign` and `near_dist` variables by dividing them by 1000. These new variables are likely to be used in subsequent steps of the analysis, that is to say the estimation of the Fuzzy RDD model.

Perform regressions

The segmentary lineage indicator $ISLe(i)$ will be use as an instrument to predict the actual share of the population belonging to the segmentary lineage group. Thus, the sample is restricted to grid cells that include respondents from the Afrobarometer surveys (who self-reported ethnicity).

Then, we want to examine the relationship between the predicted share of the population belonging to the segmentary lineage group and the outcome variable, which is conflict in this context. Let's perform a series of regressions and instrumental variable regressions using different dependent variables.

```
eststo : reg ln_sum_deadly SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg
        i.countrycode if near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est1

eststo : ivregress 2sls ln_sum_deadly (frac_seg = SL) i.pair_fe
        near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg i.countrycode if near_dist<60,
        cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est2
```

The first type of regression performed is an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, where the dependent variable is `ln_sum_deadly`. This model includes various control variables such as `pair_fe`, `near_dist_sign`, `near_dist_sign_seg`, and country fixed effects.

Next, a Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) regression is executed using the `ivregress` command. Here, `frac_seg` is used as the instrumental variable for the segmentary lineage indicator (SL). Again, the model includes control variables and country fixed effects (`ethfe` and `coufe`).

The `cluster` option is used to specify clustering by NAME for computing clustered standard errors.

(MAYBE EXPLAINING WHY WE CLUSTER ?)

```

eststo : reg ln_sum_fatal1 SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg
        i.countrycode if near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est3

eststo : ivregress 2sls ln_sum_fatal1 (frac_seg = SL) i.pair_fe
        near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg i.countrycode if near_dist<60,
        cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est4

eststo : reg ln_conflictfm SL i.pair_fe near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg
        i.countrycode if near_dist<60, cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est5

eststo : ivregress 2sls ln_conflictfm (frac_seg = SL) i.pair_fe
        near_dist_sign near_dist_sign_seg i.countrycode if near_dist<60,
        cluster(NAME)
estadd local ethfe "Yes"
estadd local coufe "Yes"
estimates store est6

```

The same steps are repeated for other dependent variables (`ln_sum_fatal1` and `ln_conflictfm`). The code is duplicated with appropriate changes for each dependent variable, and the results are stored in separate estimation objects (`est3`, `est4`, `est5`, and `est6`).

Table 3: Fuzzy RDD

	ln (1+Deadly Conflict Incidents)		ln (1+Conflict Deaths)		ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)	
	Baseline RD	Fuzzy RD (2SLS)	Baseline RD	Fuzzy RD (2SLS)	Baseline RD	Fuzzy RD (2SLS)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(mean) SL	0.0948		0.2837*		0.0692	
	(0.0810)		(0.1451)		(0.0666)	
frac_seg		0.3379		1.0114**		0.2467
		(0.2771)		(0.4931)		(0.2302)
Ethnicity Pair FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1018	1018	1018	1018	1018	1018
R-squared	0.241	0.226	0.166	0.118	0.234	0.223

Notes: Standard errors, clustered at the ethnicity level, are reported in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

The key finding from the 2SLS fuzzy RD estimation is that the effects observed are consistently about 3.5 times larger than the baseline RD estimates.

3.4 Third tests - Placebo Tests

In a Spatial Regression Discontinuity exercise, researchers usually also have to show that the results are robust towards different specifications and parameters.

"We also conduct a series of placebo tests where we examine pairs of adjacent ethnic groups that have the same segmentary lineage status but differ in other dimensions. Using the same RD estimator, we find no evidence that any of the other characteristics affect conflict."

An assumption inherent in the RD approach is the smooth variation of unobservable factors across borders. While direct testing of this assumption is impossible, we assess its validity by examining whether there is a discernible discontinuity at the border for several observable variables. These include elevation, slope, average temperature, presence of water bodies, suitability for cereal cultivation, percentage of cultivated land, presence of petroleum and diamonds, number of mission stations during early colonial times, an indicator for colonial railway presence, and an indicator for precolonial explorer routes.

Despite finding no evidence of discontinuities in geographic or historical factors, a significant concern persists: the possibility that other ethnic characteristics, beyond segmentary lineage organization, may vary discontinuously at the boundaries. For our RD estimates to be compromised, these ethnic differences must independently influence contemporary conflict. To address this concern, we conduct "placebo" estimates, mirroring the baseline RD procedure but using other ethnicity-level characteristics to create ethnicity pairs and define treatment and control.

Across all 36 specifications, the estimated effects of alternative ethnic characteristics are consistently small in magnitude and statistically insignificant. Consequently, while our RD estimates highlight a robust relationship between segmentary lineage organization and conflict, we do not find evidence that other factors, such as historical political centralization or economic development, exert an independent influence on conflict.

A Esttab

A.1 Esttab Sharp RD

```
esttab est* using "/Users/gaelperrot/Desktop/Master 2/Stata seminar/
Replicates/our/table3.tex", cells(b(fmt(4) star) se(par fmt(4)))
stats(ethfe coufe geoco N, fmt(%9.0gc %9.0gc %9.0gc %-9.0f ) label("
Ethnicity Pair FE" "Country FE" "Geographic Controls" "Observations"))
replace style(tex) label collabels(none) mlabels(none) keep(SL)
prehead( `"\begin{table}[htbp]\centering" ' `"\def\sym#1{\ifmmode^{#1}\
else\(^{#1}\)\fi}" ' `"\caption{replication of the line 1 of table 2}" '
`"\resizebox{\columnwidth}{!}{%" ' `"\begin{tabular}{1*{9}{c}}" ' `"\
toprule" ' `"\Dependent Variable: &\multicolumn{3}{c}{\ln (1+Deadly
Conflict Incidents)} &\multicolumn{3}{c}{\ln (1+Conflict Deaths)} &
\multicolumn{3}{c}{\ln (1+Months of Deadly Conflict)} \\" ' `"\
cmidrule(lr){2-4} \cmidrule(lr){5-7} \cmidrule(lr){8-10} " ' ) postfoot
(`"\bottomrule" ' `"\multicolumn{10}{l}{\footnotesize Notes: Standard
errors, clustered at the ethnicity level, are reported in parentheses.
\sym{*} \ (p<0.10\), \sym{**} \ (p<0.05\), \sym{***} \ (p<0.01\)}\\" ' `"\
end{tabular}}" ' `"\end{table}" ' )
```

A.2 Esttab Fuzzy RDD

```
esttab est* using "/Users/gaelperrot/Desktop/Master 2/Stata seminar/
Replicates/our/table4.tex", cells(b(fmt(4) star) se(par fmt(4)))
stats(ethfe coufe N r2, fmt(%9.0gc %9.0gc %-9.0f %9.3f) label("
Ethnicity Pair FE" "Country FE" "Observations" "R-squared")) replace
style(tex) label collabels(none) mlabels(none) keep(SL frac_seg )
prehead(`"\begin{table}[htbp]\centering" ' `"\def\sym#1{\ifmmode^{#1}\
else\(^{#1}\)\fi}" ' `"\caption{Fuzzy RDD}" ' `"\resizebox{\columnwidth
}{!}{%" ' `"\begin{tabular}{1*{7}{c}}" ' `"\toprule" ' ) postfoot(`"\
bottomrule" ' `"\multicolumn{7}{l}{\footnotesize Notes: Standard errors,
clustered at the ethnicity level, are reported in parentheses. \sym{*}
\ (p<0.10\), \sym{**} \ (p<0.05\), \sym{***} \ (p<0.01\)}\\" ' `"\end{
tabular}}" ' `"\end{table}" ' )
```